

Event Abstract

Childhood obesity and its relationship with dietary Behavior of the Primary School Children at Benghazi Libya

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Background: Obesity has negative health impacts in childhood, particularly for the long term. In addition to a higher risk of obesity and non-communicable diseases (NCDs) later in life, affected children experience adverse outcomes.

Aims of the study: to find out the prevalence of obesity among primary school children at Benghazi Libya (2012) and its relation with the breakfast skipping, dietary behaviors and socio-economic factors.

Subject and methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study conducted among primary school children at Benghazi 2012. Analysis of variances and longitudinal mixed-effects linear regression models were used to investigate the relation of socio-economic factors and dietary behavior with BMI.

Results: The mean age was 8.9 ± 2.2 years. The mean BMI = 32 ± 11.0 kg/m². The study revealed that about more than half of children their BMI were more than 30kg/m². The study also revealed significant relation between child obesity and skipping breakfast ($p=0.002$), negatively associated with vegetable intake ($P=0.004$), family size (0.016), and social status (0.004).

Conclusions: changing child dietary behavior and family relations are important factors in childhood obesity reduction.

Keywords: Primary School, Dietary Behaviors, Skipping Breakfast.

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